

MapGES & iAtlantic Project

Exploration of Azores deep-sea habitats, summer 2020

MapGES_2020 Cruise Report

Main objective: to explore deep-sea areas of the Azores for which there is currently little or no information available on the composition and diversity of its benthic fauna in order to better understand the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and commercial fish species in this region.

Methodology: The main device used during this cruise corresponds to the Azor drift-cam, the low-cost drifting camera system designed and developed at IMAR which allows the recording of high-quality underwater video images down to 1000 m depth. The system was deployed both from a fishing vessel and from the research vessel N/I Arquipélago, from the University of the Azores.

Chief scientist: Telmo Morato

Scientific team: Telmo Morato, Carlos Dominguez-Carrió, Sérgio Gomes, Gerald H. Taranto, Manuela Ramos, Laurence Fauconnet, Luis Rodrigues, Marina Carreiro-Silva

Cruise summary: The MapGES_2020 survey was divided in 3 different legs, which were planned to explore different areas of the Azores archipelago around the central group of islands (Table 1, Figure 1). Overall, almost 100 dives were accomplished in 8 different underwater features, which includes 6 shallow seamounts and 2 island slopes.

- Leg 1, 22 to 31 August 2020. This leg aimed to survey the slopes and small seamounts around the island of Graciosa, with one day also allocated to survey Ilha Azul seamount, an area later completed in Leg 2. The importance of Leg 1 went beyond the amount of new areas explored, but corresponded to the first time that the whole Azor drift-cam system was moved between islands using a regular ferry line and also the first full survey on board of a local fishing vessel not based in Faial island. During Leg 1, 32 dives on the slopes of Graciosa and 4 dives in Ilha Azul seamount were successfully completed (Figure 1), covering more than 17 km of seabed.
- Leg 2, 24 September to 1 October 2020. This leg also aimed to survey deep-sea areas on the northern side of the central group. After 7 days of work on board of the research vessel N/I Arquipélago, 5 different seamounts were explored, as well as the slopes on the western side of Terceira island, popularly named Serreta (Figure 1). During Leg 2, 37 dives were accomplished, covering more than 20 linear km of seabed.
- Leg 3, 20 to 26 November 2020. This leg planned to explore two underwater features south of Faial and Pico islands, for which some previous knowledge was available, especially in its deeper areas. During Leg 3, 26 dives were accomplished, 13 in Condor de Fora and 13 in Baixo de São Mateus seamounts (Figure 1), adding an extra 13.3 km of seabed surveyed.

Table 1. Areas surveyed during each of the legs of MapGES_2020 cruise, with information on the amount of underwater terrain explored and time of filming accomplished.

Leg	Dates	Areas explored	Dives	km	Bottom time (h)
1	22-31 Aug.	Slopes of Graciosa island & Ilha Azul seamount	36	17.2	25
2	24 Sept.-1 Oct.	Ilha Azul, Mar da Fortuna, Serreta and João Leonardes seamounts & W slopes of Terceira	37	22.4	27
3	20-26 Nov.	Condor de Fora and Baixo de S. Mateus seamounts	26	13.3	20.5
Total			99	52.9	72.5

Main achievements:

1. Accomplishment of almost 100 new underwater video transects between 100 and 800 m depth, most of them in areas of the Azores that had never been explored before and for which no information regarding the composition of its benthic communities was available.
2. Discovery of diverse coral gardens and sponge grounds whose presence was unknown to science and that may fit the FAO criteria to be considered Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs).
3. Successfully perform a 10-day survey with the Azor drift-cam on board of a local fishing vessel not based in Faial island, with dives to almost 800 m depth. This achievement demonstrates the great capacity of this tool, fully designed and developed at IMAR, to (a) rapidly assess the diversity of deep-sea benthic communities from small local vessels and (b) be moved between areas with ease.

Figure 1. Location of the 99 dives performed with the Azor drift-cam during the 3 legs of the MapGES_2020 survey around the islands of Graciosa and Terceira, and the seamounts Condor de Fora, Baixo de São Mateus, Ilha Azul, Mar da Fortuna, Serreta and João Leonardes. Leg 1: yellow points; Leg 2: blue points; Leg 3: red points.

Leg 1

Slopes of Graciosa island and Ilha Azul seamount on board of the fishing vessel Galinha

Objective of this leg: to explore for the first time the slopes and small seamounts around the island of Graciosa and the seamount Ilha Azul in order to better understand the distribution of VMEs and commercial fish species in this part of the Azores archipelago.

Vessel: 7-m-long local fishing vessel Galinha (based in Graciosa island)

Dates: 22-31 August 2020

Scientific team: Telmo Morato, Carlos Dominguez-Carrió, Sérgio Gomes, Gerald H. Taranto

Figure 2. Picture taken at the end of the Leg 1 on board of the fishing vessel Galinha with the scientific team and the two fishermen. The island of Graciosa can be observed in the background.

Summary of Leg 1

The objectives of the first part of MapGES_2020 survey were two-fold: first, it aimed to explore the deep seafloor around Graciosa island, which had never been visually investigated before. Second, it aimed to perform a full 10-day survey deploying the Azor drift-cam from a local fishing vessel. This was the first time in which all the components that make up the Azor drift-cam (main structure, umbilical, on-board components and spares) were moved to a different island using a conventional ferry line. Further, it was also the first time that a survey was carried out on a local fishing vessel not based in Faial island and with which no previous tests were made prior to our arrival.

To transport two full replicates of the Azor drift-cam system, only conventional pick-up trucks were used in both islands, and all the gear was transported as part of the passenger cargo of a regular ferry that completes the route Faial-Graciosa-Faial on a daily basis. The equipment was easily moved by the 4 members of the team that participated in the survey. Setting the system on the fishing vessel also represented a relatively simple task, with the open deck at the back of the vessel proving large enough to comfortably operate the system during the day (Figure 3a). The TV screen that displayed the live-view images together with PC laptops and external hard drives, used to store all the information produced, were placed inside the cabin to avoid any damages produced by adverse weather conditions and to improve the visibility of the images in daylight conditions. Information from inside the cabin to indicate the winch operators whether cable had to be released or recovered was easily achieved by means of portable radio systems (Figure 3b). The winch of the fishing vessel worked well in all sea conditions, and allowed for a relatively easy recovery after each dive (Figure 3c). The only limitation encountered related to the possibility of repairing at sea certain parts of the equipment after they got damaged (Figure 3e), primarily due to the low power of the 220V socket. Bringing spare parts of all components, especially the umbilical, represented a good decision to avoid having to go back to shore after any part of the equipment got damaged, and a simple replacement of the broken part allowed the team to continue working normally.

Figure 3. Images taken during Leg 1 on board of the fishing vessel. (a) Sailing towards a sampling station during calm weather. (b) A member of the scientific team providing indications to the winch operators. (c-d) Members of the scientific team and the boat’s crew recovering umbilical with the vessel’s winch. The weather was not favorable in all occasions. (e) A member of the scientific team fixing one of the breakages that occurred to the electrical cable during the cruise.

The first part of MapGES_2020 survey was planned to explore the deep seafloor around Graciosa island, the northernmost island of the Azores central group. This area had never been investigated in the past using underwater cameras, so Leg 1 of MapGES_2020 represented an excellent opportunity to gather crucial information

about the diversity and distribution of deep-sea benthic communities on this part of the Azores. The survey aimed to get images from all around the island, and after 6 days of work and a total of 32 dives (Table 2), only the northern slopes had to be left not surveyed (Figure 3). This related to the fact that the Azor drift-cam relies on the drift of the vessel to perform its path over the seabed, and the slopes on the northern side of the island only face northwards. The northwesterly winds that blew during most days made a transect in N-S direction almost impossible to accomplish.

Some of the areas explored revealed the presence of dense and diverse coral gardens, most of which were dominated by 4 different species of octocorals that displayed different densities across areas (Figure 5a-c). A high proportion of the corals observed in these aggregations displayed large sizes and showed very few signs of being impacted by fishing activities. Massive sponges of the genus *Characella* were also commonly observed throughout the whole area, although never seen forming dense aggregations (Figure 5d).

Figure 4. Location of the 36 video transects (black lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam on the slopes around Graciosa island (32) and in Ilha Azul seamount (4).

One day of the survey was allocated to the exploration of Ilha Azul seamount, an underwater feature located 9.5 nm from the southernmost part of Graciosa island, and for which no information was previously available. This seamount was later complemented with more dives performed during Leg 2. During one of the dives

performed in Ilha Azul, a large school of silver scabbardfish (*Lepidopus caudatus*) followed the camera system for some minutes (Figure 5e).

Several fishing lines were observed in the dives performed around Graciosa, mainly in the form of thin monofilament nylon lines. On the contrary, Ilha Azul seamount had a higher number of abandoned longlines, in one of which the Azor drift-cam got temporarily stuck before being released. No damages to the structure nor the components were reported during the cruise, besides some breakages on the umbilical, which were rapidly fixed once back at port.

Figure 5. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 1 of MapGES_2020 cruise. (a) A coral garden dominated by the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*. (b) A mixed coral garden with several species of octocorals. (c) Another common coral garden dominated by the yellow sea fan *Dentomuricea aff. meteor*. (d) A large sponge of the species cf. *Characella pachastrelloides*. (e) A school of silver scabbardfish (*Lepidopus caudatus*) that came to see the Azor drift-cam while cruising underwater. (f) One of the several deep-sea sharks that were observed during the survey.

Table 2. Metadata of the 36 dives performed with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 1 of MapGES_2020 cruise on board of the “Galinha” fishing vessel.

St.	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Start-end depth (m)	Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat.	Long.	Lat.	Long.		
01	Graciosa S	22/08	9:14:00	10:20:20	38.965	-27.985	38.965	-27.994	505-386	770
02	Graciosa S	22/08	11:07:10	12:24:20	38.940	-27.971	38.940	-27.973	710-673	110
03	Graciosa S	22/08	13:13:20	14:03:55	38.947	-27.983	38.943	-27.991	473-388	810
04	Graciosa S	22/08	14:44:55	15:09:20	38.959	-27.964	38.961	-27.965	589-550	250
05	Graciosa S	22/08	15:49:30	16:12:30	38.955	-27.966	38.955	-27.966	572-582	20
06	Graciosa S	22/08	16:59:30	17:31:50	38.971	-27.953	38.971	-27.955	670-672	110
07	Graciosa NW	23/08	9:53:35	10:23:00	39.124	-28.188	39.127	-28.185	532-548	420
08	Graciosa NW	23/08	11:03:30	12:04:00	39.115	-28.177	39.122	-28.172	526-431	890
09	Graciosa NW	23/08	12:41:10	13:47:20	39.125	-28.138	39.130	-28.129	685-490	880
10	Graciosa NW	23/08	14:22:00	15:17:50	39.130	-28.121	39.135	-28.113	582-373	900
11	Graciosa NW	23/08	15:49:30	16:49:30	39.147	-28.119	39.152	-28.110	698-516	1020
12	Graciosa E	24/08	8:34:35	9:24:50	39.062	-27.906	39.064	-27.902	732-639	440
13	Graciosa E	24/08	10:08:10	10:47:10	39.065	-27.904	39.066	-27.900	658-620	350
14	Graciosa E	24/08	11:50:25	12:28:30	39.087	-27.898	39.085	-27.894	773-722	470
15	Graciosa E	24/08	13:19:55	13:46:25	39.085	-27.926	39.087	-27.921	374-352	410
16	Graciosa E	26/08	8:16:15	9:03:45	39.072	-27.937	39.075	-27.934	330-362	350
17	Graciosa E	26/08	9:37:15	10:07:10	39.081	-27.921	39.083	-27.917	538-468	400
18	Graciosa SE	26/08	11:07:25	11:44:00	39.020	-27.897	39.020	-27.895	367-336	230
19	Graciosa SE	26/08	12:23:45	12:47:50	38.993	-27.885	38.987	-27.886	414-463	580
20	Graciosa SE	26/08	13:49:15	14:48:15	38.972	-27.899	38.973	-27.896	672-558	310
21	Graciosa SE	26/08	15:41:15	16:33:15	38.984	-27.929	38.979	-27.930	400-342	530
22	Graciosa SE	26/08	17:08:15	17:36:25	38.988	-27.913	38.984	-27.911	257-354	480
23	Ilha Azul	27/08	10:01:00	10:45:00	38.829	-27.873	38.826	-27.876	695-495	450
24	Ilha Azul	27/08	11:28:00	11:52:30	38.838	-27.894	38.837	-27.898	699-529	340

St.	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Start-end depth (m)	Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat.	Long.	Lat.	Long.		
25	Ilha Azul	27/08	13:25:35	14:25:15	38.828	-27.950	38.827	-27.955	540-751	440
26	Ilha Azul	27/08	15:16:50	15:19:25	38.855	-27.927	38.855	-27.928	500-514	30
27	Graciosa NO	28/08	9:24:40	9:57:10	39.143	-28.057	39.143	-28.050	518-496	600
28	Graciosa NO	28/08	10:52:35	11:20:35	39.152	-28.081	39.155	-28.075	600-484	550
29	Graciosa E	28/08	Aborted							
30	Graciosa W	30/08	9:49:00	10:36:00	39.092	-28.165	39.091	-28.158	594-437	620
31	Graciosa W	30/08	11:29:20	11:53:00	39.050	-28.151	39.049	-28.148	698-682	300
32	Graciosa W	30/08	12:40:40	13:33:05	39.036	-28.118	39.031	-28.116	616-536	570
33	Graciosa W	30/08	14:20:10	15:17:00	39.021	-28.111	39.017	-28.104	630-295	710
34	Graciosa W	30/08	15:54:30	16:19:15	39.027	-28.124	39.023	-28.122	706-643	470
35	Graciosa W	31/08	8:57:20	9:33:40	39.002	-28.108	38.999	-28.106	503-366	350
36	Graciosa S	31/08	10:55:00	12:02:25	38.969	-28.095	38.963	-28.093	598-510	650
37	Graciosa S	31/08	13:22:15	13:52:30	38.987	-27.981	38.983	-27.983	423-299	400

Leg 2

Ilha Azul, Mar da Fortuna and Serreta seamounts on board of N/I Arquipélago

Objective of this leg: to explore deep-sea areas north of the central group of islands, including the seamounts Ilha Azul, Mar da Fortuna, João Leonardes and Serreta, and the slopes west of Terceira island in order to better understand the distribution patterns of VMEs and commercial fish species in this part of the Azores region.

Vessel: N/I Arquipélago (University of the Azores)

Dates: 24 September - 1 October 2020

Scientific team: Telmo Morato, Sérgio Gomes, Gerald H. Taranto, Manuela Ramos, Laurence Fauconnet

Main achievements:

1. Exploration of over 22 km of seabed down to 800 m depth in several seamounts and island slopes for which no information of its benthic communities was available
2. Discovery of new sites that host rich coral gardens and sponge grounds that were unknown to science, some of which could fit the FAO definition of what constitutes a Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME)

Figure 6. Picture taken at the end of Leg 2 of MapGES cruise on board of N/I Arquipélago, with the scientific team and the crew of the research vessel.

Summary of Leg 2

Leg 2 aimed to continue the exploratory work carried out on the northern side of the central group of islands of the Azores region that started in Leg 1. This time, the work focused on the seamounts located north of Graciosa and Terceira islands, where no data regarding its benthic communities obtained by means of visual methods was available to date. This exploratory survey targeted several different

seamounts, although rough weather conditions limited the work done in the areas furthest offshore (Borda and Sedlo seamounts). Instead, some areas close to Terceira island were selected in order to maximize the ship time. In the end, a total of 37 dives were performed in 7 days of work, covering almost 22.5 km of seabed (Table 3).

Table 3. Metadata of the 37 dives performed with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 2 of MapGES_2020 cruise on board of the research vessel N/I Arquipélago.

St.	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Start-end depth (m)	Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat.	Long.	Lat.	Long.		
38	Ilha Azul	24/09	14:50	15:45	38.839	-27.926	38.835	-27.933	483-524	710
39	Ilha Azul	24/09	16:23	17:27	38.828	-27.914	38.825	-27.924	429-397	910
40	Ilha Azul	24/09	18:11	19:25	38.850	-27.901	38.844	-27.910	689-468	1010
41	Mar Fortuna	25/09	8:28	8:55	39.068	-27.578	39.082	-27.581	562-584	1620
42	Mar Fortuna	25/09	9:35	10:50	39.082	-27.581	39.084	-27.586	578-512	440
43	Mar Fortuna	25/09	11:35	12:30	39.049	-27.560	39.049	-27.568	558-647	740
44	Mar Fortuna	25/09	13:07	13:33	39.051	-27.558	39.052	-27.563	449-486	400
45	Mar Fortuna	25/09	14:33	15:35	39.066	-27.566	39.069	-27.580	295-429	1270
46	Mar Fortuna	25/09	16:24	17:00	39.043	-27.542	39.045	-27.545	522-397	350
47	Terceira Serreta	26/09	9:10	9:18	38.738	-27.419	38.739	-27.420	744-706	120
48	Terceira Serreta	26/09	11:25	12:13	38.756	-27.412	38.760	-27.419	510-500	740
49	Terceira Serreta	26/09	14:10	15:20	38.770	-27.422	38.783	-27.427	429-105	1450
50	Terceira Serreta	26/09	15:51	17:12	38.782	-27.465	38.788	-27.469	528-347	750
51	Terceira Serreta	26/09	17:53	18:33	38.792	-27.480	38.797	-27.485	405-358	730
52	Serreta	27/09	8:14	8:51	39.213	-27.282	39.218	-27.284	708-734	630
53	Serreta	27/09	9:31	9:58	39.223	-27.277	39.228	-27.277	640-662	480
54	Serreta	27/09	10:44	11:22	39.222	-27.267	39.227	-27.268	695-614	550
55	Serreta	27/09	12:04	12:31	39.234	-27.265	39.238	-27.268	672-688	590
56	João Leonardes	27/09	15:06	15:57	39.406	-27.041	39.410	-27.043	794-689	500
57	João Leonardes	27/09	Aborted							
58	NE Terceira	28/09	16:05	16:58	38.780	-27.981	38.774	-27.985	665-448	720
59	NE Terceira	28/09	17:51	19:13	38.806	-27.048	38.800	-27.058	568-173	1100
60	Terceira Serreta	30/09	8:18	8:39	38.813	-27.394	38.812	-27.393	449-386	110
61	Terceira Serreta	30/09	9:02	9:27	38.815	-27.393	38.814	-27.388	380-377	430
62	Terceira Serreta	30/09	10:27	10:51	38.837	-27.433	38.837	-27.429	670-578	360
63	Terceira Serreta	30/09	11:23	12:07	38.832	-27.428	38.833	-27.420	575-489	710
64	Terceira Serreta	30/09	12:46	13:21	38.807	-27.445	38.808	-27.438	419-364	640
65	Terceira Serreta	30/09	13:58	14:18	38.823	-27.441	38.822	-27.436	736-723	390
66	Terceira Serreta	30/09	15:05	15:38	38.807	-27.472	38.805	-27.469	408-336	300
67	Terceira Serreta	30/09	16:10	16:25	38.813	-27.491	38.812	-27.491	632-609	110
68	Terceira Serreta	30/09	17:00	17:57	38.808	-27.504	38.803	-27.507	573-556	640
69	Ilha Azul	01/10	8:35	9:15	38.763	-27.721	38.762	-27.721	784-777	90
70	Ilha Azul	01/10	10:02	10:44	38.759	-27.724	38.757	-27.723	708-708	220
71	Ilha Azul	01/10	11:18	11:39	38.751	-27.723	38.751	-27.723	646-653	90
72	Ilha Azul	01/10	13:57	15:02	38.831	-27.954	38.826	-27.950	564-547	690
73	Ilha Azul	01/10	15:50	16:57	38.864	-27.948	38.857	-27.949	683-578	760
74	Ilha Azul	01/10	17:39	18:55	38.837	-27.972	38.828	-27.969	658-654	1050

Two days of work were allocated to finalize the exploratory survey started in Ilha Azul seamount during Leg 1. In 1.5 days, 7 new dives down to 700 m were performed (Figure 7). Two more days were allocated for the other 3 seamounts located further north, generating 5 new dives in Mar da Fortuna, 4 in Serreta and just one in João Leonardes (Figure 7). These seamounts had several abandoned fishing lines, and during dive 46 in Mar da Fortuna seamount, when moving the system upwards trying to avoid a large overhang, the drift-cam got entangled in a fishing line suspended over the seabed. Despite the massive efforts done by the crew to get the system free, it was not possible to bring it back on board. With a full new system up and running, the slopes of Terceira island were explored, with most effort placed on the north-western side, an area known by the locals as “Serreta da

Terceira”. A total of 14 dives were performed, covering 7.5 km of seabed between 100 and 750 m depth (Figure 7). Two extra dives were carried out on the north-eastern slopes, aiming to get a better idea of the distribution of benthic communities around this island.

Figure 7. Location of the 37 underwater video transects (black lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 2 of MapGES_2020 survey in the seamounts Ilha Azul, Mar da Fortuna, Serreta and João Leonardes, and on the western and northern slopes of Terceira island.

Leg 2 of MapGES_2020 corresponded to the second time the Azor drift-cam was used in the research vessel N/I Arquipélago (Figure 8). The drifting-camera system worked well again during the whole cruise, accomplishing more than 5 dives per day on average, which corresponds to more than 3 km of seabed explored per day. Besides the problems encountered during dive 46 in Mar da Fortuna seamount, with the loss of one full system, only minor problems can be reported (e.g. cameras and voltage regulators stopped working), all of which could be identified and overcome by the team members on board.

The images recorded provide an idea of the type of benthic communities that can be found in seamounts located north of the Azores, historically targeted by the fishing fleet, especially those closer to shore. Several structurally complex octocoral gardens were discovered, some of which in a very good conservation status, which could fit the FAO criteria to be considered Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (some examples provided in Figure 9). Since most of the areas visited had never been explored before, the analysis of the video images recorded with the Azor drift-cam will generate a step forward in understanding the distribution patterns of VMEs in this region of the Azores and across the whole EEZ.

Figure 8. Images taken during Leg 2 on board of the research vessel N/I Arquipélago. (a) Members of the scientific team planning a new dive based on the bathymetry and the drift of the vessel. (b) Members of the scientific team and the crew of the vessel getting ready to deploy the Azor drift-cam. (c) A member of the scientific team observing the images of the live-view system in order to provide indications to the winch operators.

Figure 9. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 2 of MapGES_2020 cruise. (a) A rocky outcrop with *Pleurocorallium johnsoni* and cf. *Poecillastra compressa*. (b) A mixed coral garden with *Viminella flagellum* and *Dentomuricea* cf. *meteor*. (c) Aggregation of *Acanthogorgia* sp. on large boulders and rocks. (d) A dense coral garden with *Narella bellissima* and *Narella versluysi*. (e) Large colonies of the primnoid coral *Callogorgia verticillata*. (f) Glass sponges of the species *Pheronema carpenteri* with the octocoral *Narella versluysi*.

Leg 3

Condor de Fora and Baixo de São Mateus seamounts on board of N/I Arquipélago (20-26 November 2020)

Objective of this leg: to start the exploration of the seamount complex area south of Faial and Pico islands. This large area is the most important bottom fishing ground in the Azores, where many lost fishing lines are expected to be found posing threats to our sampling device. Specifically, we aimed to explore the Condor de Fora and Baixo de São Mateus seamounts in order to better understand the distribution patterns of VMEs and commercial fish species in this part of the Azores archipelago.

Vessel: N/I Arquipélago (University of the Azores)

Scientific team: Telmo Morato, Sérgio Gomes, Gerald H. Taranto, Manuela Ramos, Luis Rodrigues

Main achievements:

1. Exploration of over 13 km of seabed down to 750 m depth in two shallow seamounts highly frequented by the fishing fleet and for which little information regarding the composition of its benthic communities was available
2. Discovery of new sites that host coral gardens and sponge grounds that were unknown to science

Summary of Leg 3

Leg 3 of MapGES_2020 was performed during the second half of the month of November, when sea conditions in the Azores tend to be difficult, especially to perform video surveys. Making use of a window of good weather, Leg 3 started the exploration of the seamount complex area south of Faial and Pico islands. This large area is the most important bottom fishing ground in the Azores, where many lost fishing lines are expected to be found posing threats to our sampling device. It focused on exploring two elongated seamounts located just a few miles south of Faial: Condor de Fora and Baixo de São Mateus (Figure 10). Two days of work were allocated per seamount, achieving a total of 26 dives altogether.

In Condor de Fora seamount, the 13 dives performed between 380 and 760 m depth generated more than 9 hours of seabed video footage, which corresponds to more than 5.5 km of seafloor explored (Table 4). In Baixo de São Mateus, the 13 dives performed between 360 and 640 m depth generated more than 11 hours of seabed video footage, which corresponds to more than 7.5 km of seafloor explored (Table 4). No problems were reported during this leg of the cruise, with the Azor drift-cam working perfectly throughout the four days of work at sea. Only one incident can be reported, when the system got stuck in a fishing line (dive 87) in Condor de Fora Seamount. The work of the crew manoeuvring the vessel and the winch was sufficient to release the system from the fishing line with the only loss of the bottom weight. No issues were observed neither to the structure nor the components once the system was back on deck.

Figure 10. Location of the 26 underwater video transects (black lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam on board of N/I Arquipélago during Leg 3 of MapGES_2020 survey. The two seamounts explored correspond to in the seamounts Condor de Fora (13 dives) and Baixo de São Mateus (13 dives).

The benthic communities observed in these two seamounts were in general less structurally complex than those identified in Leg 2, with a higher percentage of bottoms dominated by large erect sponges and a smaller number of structurally complex coral gardens identified. Some examples of the benthic communities observed are given in Figure 11. The evaluation of the images recorded with the Azor drift-cam in those two seamounts will provide key information on the composition of benthic communities on this area of the Azores and provide clues to understand the distribution of benthic communities at the scale of the whole archipelago.

Table 4. Metadata of the 26 dives performed with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 3 of MapGES_2020 cruise on board of the research vessel N/I Arquipélago.

St.	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Start-end depth (m)	Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat.	Long.	Lat.	Long.		
78	Condor de Fora	20/11	08:38	09:35	38.373	-28.899	38.368	-28.906	760-554	790
79	Condor de Fora	20/11	10:17	11:11	38.365	-28.943	38.360	-28.948	674-549	720
80	Condor de Fora	20/11	11:47	12:27	38.359	-28.948	38.357	-28.951	507-396	310
81	Condor de Fora	20/11	13:57	14:33	38.363	-28.993	38.362	-28.996	655-524	350
82	Condor de Fora	20/11	15:24	16:07	38.361	-28.997	38.360	-29.000	445-381	230
83	Condor de Fora	20/11	16:46	17:37	38.350	-28.965	38.352	-28.966	636-602	210
84	Condor de Fora	21/11	08:37	09:10	38.360	-29.070	38.360	-29.071	574-586	80
85	Condor de Fora	21/11	09:40	10:11	38.363	-29.068	38.362	-29.073	508-531	420
86	Condor de Fora	21/11	10:42	11:27	38.363	-29.076	38.364	-29.081	578-630	470
87	Condor de Fora	21/11	12:12	13:11	38.360	-29.021	38.361	-29.031	451-433	890
88	Condor de Fora	21/11	14:15	15:01	38.358	-28.996	38.360	-29.003	412-392	640
89	Condor de Fora	21/11	15:46	16:25	38.346	-28.962	38.349	-28.966	545-575	420
90	Condor de Fora	21/11	17:11	17:37	38.367	-28.930	38.368	-28.932	686-665	150

St.	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Start-end depth (m)	Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat.	Long.	Lat.	Long.		
91	B. São Mateus	23/11	08:23	09:33	38.304	-28.487	38.299	-28.490	546-486	600
92	B. São Mateus	23/11	10:18	10:33	38.328	-28.532	38.328	-28.533	619-624	100
93	B. São Mateus	23/11	11:11	11:58	38.338	-28.553	38.344	-28.554	606-643	490
94	B. São Mateus	23/11	12:41	13:41	38.319	-28.579	38.325	-28.575	449-364	720
95	B. São Mateus	23/11	14:30	15:36	38.309	-28.564	38.311	-28.559	579-463	520
96	B. São Mateus	23/11	16:14	17:15	38.328	-28.582	38.328	-28.571	367-362	950
97	B. São Mateus	26/11	08:18	09:01	38.333	-28.585	38.329	-28.580	412-364	640
98	B. São Mateus	26/11	09:29	10:01	38.327	-28.590	38.322	-28.586	373-430	590
99	B. São Mateus	26/11	10:37	11:24	38.336	-28.615	38.330	-28.613	391-442	690
100	B. São Mateus	26/11	11:57	12:59	38.340	-28.646	38.332	-28.645	402-529	850
101	B. São Mateus	26/11	13:47	14:49	38.377	-28.662	38.373	-28.658	611-602	560
102	B. São Mateus	26/11	15:27	16:34	38.372	-28.672	38.371	-28.666	605-574	550
103	B. São Mateus	26/11	17:10	17:42	38.360	-28.670	38.358	-28.666	533-513	340

Figure 11. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 3 of MapGES_2020 cruise. (a) Aggregation of the glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* with the octocoral *Narella versluysi*. (b) A large colony of the primnoid coral *Callogorgia verticillata*. (c) A large sponge of the species cf. *Characella pachastrelloides*. (d) Sponges assemblage on hard substrate. (e) A deep-sea shark swimming in front of the camera. (f) Aggregation of fishes of the species *Capros aper* following the camera system on a soft bottom area.